

Past academic and research activities

2002 – 2020

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(for purpose of transparency)

2020

- 06. Sep : Conference: "Planetary Science: The Young Solar System". Click [here](#).
- 01. Jun : Workshop. Invited lecturer. EPAR: Exploration Program in Astrophysics Research (EPAR): Click [here](#).

2019

- 11. Nov : Public outreach activity at Chungnam National University: 2019 Transit of Mercury. Presenting live video broadcast from Chile in collaboration with Dr. Jeremy Tregloan-Reed. Click [here](#).
- 16. Oct : Public outreach activity: SEM International Science Festival.
- 26. Sep : Member of examination committee for MSc student Pia Cortes-Zuleta, Departamento Astronomia, Universidad de Chile, Santiago, Chile.
- 04. Aug : Invited workshop-lecturer at the 7th Vietnam School of Astrophysics: [Click here](#). Title: Planetary Science. 04. - 10. Aug. 2019, Quy Nhon, Vietnam.
- 26. Jul : Book review for MIT Press: "Moving Planets Around". More info here later.
- 11. Jul : Public tour around Daejeon Observatory & Planetarium for SEM International. Number of participants: 10 - 15. Pics: (to be added later).
- 15. Jun : Initiation of research project with DSHS: Installation of spectroscopic meteor observation system.
- 06. Jun : Discovery of two transiting planets: Click [here](#).
- 12. Feb. Public outreach lecture at Daejeon Observatory & Planetarium: "The Solar System: Life on other planets and moons?", Daejeon, South Korea.
- 09. Feb : Public outreach lecture at Daejeon Observatory & Planetarium: "Navigating Winter Night-sky: winter constellations and deep sky objects", Daejeon, South Korea.
- 20. Jan : Public outreach lecture at Daejeon Observatory & Planetarium: "Practical Astronomy: Connecting with the Sky", Daejeon, South Korea. Pics: 1,2,3,4.... (to be added later).
- 10. Jan : Start of organizing planetary science conference in Vietnam: [Click here](#).

2018

- 23. Nov : Public outreach talk and Q&A at Taedeok Highschool, Daejeon, Republic of Korea.
- 15. Sep : European Planetary Science Conference, Berlin. [Abstract](#). Title: "Possible discovery of two transiting planets around a late K-type (K2) star", Herath & Hinse et al. (2018).
- 02.-11. Sep : Remote observations with the Danish 1.54m telescope at ESO/La Silla Observatory, Chile.
- 13. Aug : In the media: [Tracking the cosmic fireworks](#). Media interview / expert opinion.
- 13. Aug : In the media: [Celestial treat: Everything you need to know about the Perseids meteor shower](#). Media interview/expert opinion.
- 05. Aug : On-site astronomical observations at the Danish 1.54m telescope at ESO/La Silla observatory, Chile.
- 25. Jul : Hands-on teaching assistant at the [2018 Carl Sagan Workshop](#), Caltech, California, USA.
- 01. Jul : Visiting scientist at Chungnam National University, Department of Astronomy and Space Science, Daejeon, South Korea.
- 30. Jun : Last day at KASI!
- Jun/Jul : Review work for A&A and MNRAS.
- 15. May : Remote observations (2 weeks) with the Danish 1.54m telescope at ESO/La Silla observatory, Chile.
- 13. Mar.: Research proposal review, National Science Center, Poland.
- 25. Feb.: workshop lecturer, conference SOC & session chair. Conference [Exoplanet Science 2018 \(Feb. 25 - Mar. 2\)](#), Quy Nhon, Vietnam.
- 26. Jan.: Science outreach talk at Daejeon Christian International Highschool, Daejeon, South Korea. Click [here](#), [here](#) and [here](#) and [here](#) and [here](#). Lecture PDF click [here](#).

2017

- 08. Dec.: Invited one-day workshop at Korea Science Academy (KSA/KAIIST) in Busan on installation of meteor detection using Raspberry Pi3.
- 22. Nov.: External reviewer for MNRAS journal manuscript.
- 12. Sep.: Poster presentation at the KAS fall meeting, Expo-park, Jeosu, South Korea.
- 01. Sep.: Remote observations (2 weeks) with Danish 1.54m telescope at ESO/La Silla observatory, Chile. MINDSTEP collaboration.
- 28. Aug.: Expert opinion/quote in The Telegraph (India) Know How section, public outreach, [The Telegraph \(India\)](#). Click [here](#) for the print version.
- 18. Aug.: Half-day workshop (expert consultation) on "Image registration and Astrometry for Meteor Detection" with four high-school students from [Korea Science Academy \(KSA/KAIIST\)](#), Busan. For meeting pics click [here](#) and [here](#).
- 15. Aug.: Prepared for a one-day KASI workshop on "Microlensing modeling with NASA's WFIRST data" (based on the Sagan workshop) planned to be given to the KASI/VO group.
- 07. Aug.: Hands-on teaching assistant at the [2017 Carl Sagan Workshop](#), Caltech, California, USA.
- 20. Jul.: Onsite observations with Danish 1.54m telescope at ESO/La Silla observatory, Chile. MINDSTEP collaboration.
- 15. May : BOAO and SOAO meteor cameras are switched off due to potential threat of lightning strikes during Korean summer season.
- 08. Apr : Poster presentation: A 2017 Ganymede Stellar Occultation Event. Data taken with Korean-based SOAO (0.60m) telescope. European Geosciences Union General Assembly 2017. [Meeting abstract](#). [Poster](#).
- 01. Mar.: Organizing member of SOC of conference [Exoplanet Science 2018 \(Feb. 25 - Mar. 2\)](#), Quy Nhon, Vietnam.

2016

- 31. Dec.: Research high-light on the discovery of the circumbinary planet Kepler-1647 in KASI 2016 Annual Report. Click [here](#).
- 28. Dec.: Book release (Korea) published by the Korea Foundation for the Advancement of Science and Creativity (KOFAC). Pictures: [Pic01](#), [Pic02](#), [Pic03](#). Link: Click [here](#) and [here](#). Click [here](#) for the first 12 pages as a PDF file. For online ordering click [here](#) or click [here](#).
- 09. Nov.: Popular science talk at Daejeon Jeonmin Highschool, Daejeon, South Korea. Pictures: [Pic01](#), [Pic02](#), [Pic03](#), [Pic04](#).
- 22. Oct.: Public outreach - Daejeon Science Festival - SEM International Science Fair, Daejeon, EXPO City, South Korea. Pictures: [Pic01](#), [Pic02](#), [Pic03](#), [Pic04](#), [Pic05](#), [Pic06](#), [Pic07](#), [Pic08](#), [Pic09](#).
- 21. Oct.: SOAO meteor detection cameras online for 2016/2017 season.
- 30. Sep.: Host to Max Joshua ([TWINKLE](#), [Blue Skies Space Ltd](#), London, UK). Colloquium on the TWINKLE space telescope.
- 26. Sep.: BOAO meteor detection cameras online for 2016/2017 season.
- 26. Aug.: Remote observations (2 weeks) with the Danish 1.54m telescope at ESO/La Silla observatory, Chile.
- 01. Aug.: Observing stay (MINDSTEP) at ESO/La Silla, Chile.
- 15. July: Teaching instructor/helper at [2016 Sagan Summerschool workshop](#), NExSci/JPL, California Institute of Technology, Pasadena, USA, CA.
- 16. June: Press release, Armagh Observatory on [Kepler-1647](#).
- 13. June: Press coverage on the discovery of Kepler-1647 in the [Guardian](#). The article covers KASI in full spelling.
- 03. June: Popular science talk at Taedeok Science Highschool, Daejeon, South Korea. Pictures: [Pic01](#), [Pic02](#), [Pic03](#), [Pic04](#), [Pic05](#), [Pic06](#), [PDF](#)
- 01. June: SOAO and BOAO meteor detection camera system is switched off due to lightning strike risk.
- 12. March: SEM International public tour around KASI. Pictures: [Pic01](#), [Pic02](#), [Pic03](#), [Pic04](#), [Pic05](#), [Pic06](#), [Pic07](#), [Pic08](#), [Pic09](#), [Pic10](#), [Pic11](#), [Pic12](#).

2015

- 24. December: KASI magazine coverage on R&E meteor detection program, Winter 2015, p. 20, vol. 20. Click [here](#).
- 03. December: Popular science talk at Torun Highschool (Mikolaja Kopernika Gimnazjum i Liceum Akademickie), Torun, Poland.
- 30. November: Seminar talk at TCFA/Nicolai Copernicus University, Torun, Poland. Click [here](#).
- 28. October: Press/news coverage in Daejeon Ilbo newspaper on meteor detection project. Click [here](#).
- Oct.-Dec.: Visiting scientist at Institute for Astronomy, Nicolai Copernicus University, Torun, Poland.
- 15. September: KASI magazine coverage on Kepler-453b, Fall 2015, p. 12, vol. 19. Click [here](#).
- 31. Aug.: Remote observations (2 weeks) with the Danish 1.54m telescope at ESO/La Silla observatory, Chile.
- 20. August: Press release on Kepler-453b. Click [here](#) or [here](#).
- 01. August: Contract change to Senior Scientist at KASI.
- 01. August: On-site observations with Danish 1.54m telescope at ESO/La Silla Observatory, Chile.
- 27. July: Hands-on exercise instructor at Sagan Summer School Workshop, Caltech, USA.
- 27. July: Poster presentation at Sagan Summer School Workshop, Caltech, USA.
- 15. July: External supervisor to MSc student Beom-Kyu Choi, Kyungpook National University, Daegu, South Korea.
- June/July: Teaching: Supervision of summer internship student Ana Sirico, University of Sao Paulo, Brasil.
- 15. June: Teaching: R&E teaching 2015 (ending in december 2015), Daejeon Science Highschool, Korea. Click [here](#).
- 15. May: Passed (award winning student price) regional competition of 61. Korea National Science Competition/Festival, Daejeon, South Korea. Project: Meteor detection in South Korea. Click [here](#).
- 15. April: Poster/talk presentation at Spring 2015 meeting of the Korea Astronomy Society. Send an email to request poster in PDF.
- 21. January: 1st presentation at regional science competition at daejeon science and education institute.
- 11-20. January: Review of ApJ paper.
- 10. January: R&E project (detection and characterisation of meteors) was awarded 2nd price at Daejeon Science Highschool, Daejeon, South Korea.

2014

- R&E prize award (silver medal) at DSHS Young Scientist Award Competition (PDF exist).
- 15. December: Popular astronomy/science talk at [Life-Skolen](#) in Toenning, Southern Slesvig, Germany.
- 11. December: Seminar talk at [Aarhus University](#) (Denmark). Click [here](#) for more information.
- 08. December: Seminar talk at [STARPLAN](#) (University of Copenhagen, Denmark). Click [here](#) for more information.
- 04. December: Finalisation of R&E project. Final report can be downloaded [here](#) (written in Korean language).
- Participation in national/regional science competition, Daejeon, South Korea.
- 15. - 19. November 2014: Installation of BOAO Meteor Detection Camera System at BOAO Observatory, South Korea (see pictures on my Facebook page)
- 17. - 23. October 2014: Installation of SOAO Meteor Detection Camera System at SOAO Observatory, South Korea (see pictures on my Facebook page)
- 16. October 2014: Talk at Korea Astronomical Society 2014 Autumn Meeting, Jeju Island, South Korea. Title: "5-body Dynamics in the Kepler-47 System: Predicting Stable Orbits of a 3rd Circumbinary Planet". Click [here](#) for a picture.
- Sep. 2014: Remote observations with the Danish 1.54m telescope at ESO/La Silla Observatory, Chile.
- 12. September 2014: KASI Best Post-Doc Award 2014.
- August 2014: Observing within MINDSTEP collaboration using DK1.54m telescope at ESO/La Silla.
- July 2014: Student instructor at Sagan Summerschool Workshop at Caltech/Pasadena.
- June 2014: PI of R&E (Research & Education) programme between Daejeon Science Highschool and KASI: "Developing a National Korea Double-station Meteor Detection Camera System"
- 01. June 2014: Featuring in a popular science article on "Irregular satellites" ([Korean Dong-A Science Magazine](#).) Pictures: [Pic1](#), [Pic2](#), [Pic3](#), [Pic4](#)
- 16. May 2014: Popular science talk at Daejeon Science Highschool, Daejeon, South Korea. Pictures: [Pic1](#), [Pic2](#), [Pic3](#), [Pic4](#)

2013

- 21. November 2013: Colloquium/seminar (search "Hinse") at [Indian Institute of Astrophysics, Bangalore, India](#). Also click [here](#).
- 08. November 2013: Outreach science talk at Daejeon Science Highschool, Daejeon, South Korea. Pictures: [Pic1](#), [Pic2](#), [Pic3](#), [Pic4](#), [Pic5](#), [Pic6](#).
- 22. October 2013: Colloquium/talk at German Aerospace Center (DLR), Berlin-Adlershof, Germany.
- Sep. 2013: Remote observations with the Danish 1.54m telescope at ESO/La Silla Observatory, Chile.
- 19-23. Aug. 2013: [Contributed talk](#) at the International Workshop MODEST-13, Almaty, Republic of Kazakhstan
- 13-14. June 2013: [Contributed talk](#) at Workshop on Solar System Small Bodies, Seoul National University, Seoul, Republic of Korea
- 12. June 2013: Obtained [membership](#) of the Kepler Eclipsing Binary Working Group (EBWG)
- 02-07 June 2013: [Poster presentation](#) at [IAU Symposium 299](#), Victoria, British-Columbia, Canada
- 12. April 2013: Talk at Korea Astronomical Society 2013 Spring Meeting, Daecheon, South Korea. Title: "Photometric Follow-up Observations of Transiting Planets using Heavy Defocus Technique"
- 12. April 2013: [Excellent TEP light curve of HAT-P-12 using 1.0m scope at Tian Shan Observatory, Rep. of Kazakhstan](#)
- 20. March 2013: [Excellent TEP light curve of HAT-P-36 using a 0.6m scope](#)

2012

- 31. December 2012: [Best Project Team 2012 - Group Achievement Award 2012](#)
- 31. December 2012: [KASI Best Post-doc Award 2012](#)
- 26. November 2012: Seminar/colloquium at NASA Astrobiology Institute, University of Hawaii-Manoa, USA. Title: "Detection and dynamical aspects of circumbinary planets/companions".
- 12. November - 20. December: Visiting scientist/Research stay at University of Hawaii, USA
- 18. October: Contributed talk at Korea Astronomy Society Fall Meeting, Gwangju, Rep. of Korea.
- 07. - 11. October: SOAO observations
- 04. October: Seminar/talk at [Yonsei University](#), Rep. of Korea
- 21. September - 24. September 2012: Testing remote observing of Dk 1.5m telescope at ESO/La Silla, Chile from Rep. of Korea (KASI).
- 03. - 06. September 2012: LOAO observations
- 23. - 31. August 2012: Contributed talk@IAU meeting in Beijing, China
- 02. August 2012: Group meeting seminar @ KASI
- 31. July 2012: Seminar at NASA Ames Research Center, USA
- 22. - 27. July 2012: Invited teaching assistant at the [Carl Sagan Summer School Workshop](#) at NExSci, CalTech, Pasadena, California, USA.
- 06. June 2012: Public outreach at KASI: Public Viewing of Venus 2012 Transit. [PDE](#). For pictures click [here](#) (may load slow).
- 04. June 2012: Press coverage on Venus Transit in [The Korea Herald](#) or click [here](#) for a PDF copy.
- 21. May 2012: Observation of partial solar eclipse from Jeju Island (South Korea). Here are some pictures: [Pic1](#), [Pic2](#), [Pic3](#), [Pic4](#), [Pic5](#), [Pic6](#), [Pic7](#), [Pic8](#)
- 15. May 2012: Public Outreach: Research profile article in KASI magazine (May/June 2012 issue). Click [here](#) for a PDF copy.
- 07. May 2012: Press release, [Work Experience students observe unusual double star](#)
- 04. May 2012: Submitted HW Vir stability paper to MNRAS.
- 13. - 16. April 2012: Observing trip to BOAO (1.8m), Rep. of Korea.
- 05. April 2012: [Initiated photometric follow-up observations of HW Vir using 2m Faulkes Telescope at Siding Spring, Australia](#)
- 25. March 2012: Obtained excellent transit light-curve of XO-1 using CbNUO 0.6m telescope. RMS=1.9 mmag.
- 22. March 2012: Public outreach activity: Guided tour around KASI. Thai Young Astronomers Ambassador Event (with Surangkhan). See my FB site for pictures.
- 01. March 2012: Popular Science Article (in Danish) on Earth Trojan asteroids, published in [KVANT No 1](#), March 2012.
- 29. February 2012: Selected as KASI post-doc of the month.
- 27. February 2012: Achieved 2mmag photometric precision of the XO-2b exo-planetary transit using the 0.6m wide-field telescope at CbNUO.
- 24. - 27. February 2012: Observing trip to BOAO (1.8m), Republic of Korea.
- 11. - 19. February 2012: Research visit at Delhi University, Prof. Avindra Singh, dynamics of exoplanets.
- 05. February 2012: Initiated research collaboration with Dr. Jonathan Horner on the stability of HW Vir.
- 01. January 2012: Obtained a 2+1 year [KRCF](#) (Korea Research Council of Fundamental Science & Technology) Young Scientist Research Fellowship.

2011

- 24. December 2011: Observed near-Earth asteroid "Phaethon" using 1.8m BOAO reflector.
- 24. December 2011: Achieved sub-millimagnitude photometric precision (0.94 mmag) of the XO-3b exo-planetary transit using the 1.8m BOAO telescope.
- 15. November 2011: Test observations of Jovian irregular satellites with Choi Jin using the roof-top near-Earth satellite telescope at KASI. Observing faint irregulars seems intractable. However, observing the motion of Galilean satellites seems feasible especially for didactic purposes.
- 10. November 2011: Oral 20min presentation at the Annual 2011 MiNDSTEP meeting in Doha (via Skype).
- 26. November 2011: Organised (with Anestis) the public live viewing (at KASI) of the Curiosity NASA Atlas V Rocket Launch from Florida, USA.
- 24. October 2011: Submitted HU Aqr paper to MNRAS.
- 12. October 2011: Public outreach: Popular astronomy talk to a 6th grade class at Nykoebing Primary School, Denmark.
- 10. October 2011: Seminar/talk (on irregular satellites) at the Center for Star and Planet Formation, Niels Bohr Institute, University of Copenhagen, Denmark.
- 10. - 19. October 2011: Research stay at University of Copenhagen, Denmark MiNDSTEP update, transiting planet, thesis advising.
- 02. - 07. October 2011: AAS/DPS Conference Nantes, France. Presenting a poster on the long-term chaotic diffusion of Jovian irregular satellites.
- 01. - 04. September 2011: Observing trip to BOAO.
- 15. August 2011: Started research project on HU Aqr.
- 09. - 25. July 2011: Observing trip to ESO, La Silla, Chile. Transiting planets, eclipsing binaries & microlensing events. Testing defocus observations of the eclipsing binary system RV Gru.
- 19. June 2011: Meeting with Dr. Cho Sungki (KASI Director of Public Outreach), Dr. Bernardo Cervantes-Sodi & Dr. Kim Ho-Il on the Venus Transit June 2012.
- 12. June 2011: Public Outreach: Guided tour for BOSCH KOREA of KASI and its observing facility - "Looking Astronomers over their Shoulders".
- 31. May 2011: Applied for telescope time at Mt. Lemmon (1.0m, LOAO) and Bohyunsan (BOAO, 1.8m).
- 13. May 2011: Institute colloquium/talk at Purple Mountain Observatory, Nanjing, China.
- 10. May 2011: Institute colloquium/talk at Wuhan University of Science & Technology.
- 01. February - 01. June 2011: Collaboration/training on microlensing modeling with Prof. Cheongho Han, Chungbuk National University, Rep. of Korea.
- 10. January 2011: Arrived at KASI, Republic of Korea, working on circumbinary extrasolar planets within a KASI post-doctoral fellowship.

2010

- Dec. 2010: [PhD Graduation Ceremony, Queens University Belfast, UK](#)
- Dec. 2010: [Lunch talk at Queen Mary University London, UK](#)
- Oct. 2010: [Visiting Keele University, UK](#)
- Oct. 2010: [Institute Seminar at IMCCE, Paris, France](#)
- Oct. 2010: [Lyot Conference, Paris, France](#)
- Aug. 2010: [Public Tours, Armagh Observatory, European Heritage Day](#)
- Sep. - Nov. 2010: [Teaching/advising work-experience students at Armagh Observatory: Observing Jovian irregular satellites with the Faulkes Telescope South](#)
- Sep. 2010: [LOC at the 2010 International Meteor Conference, Armagh Observatory, UK](#)
- July 2010: [2010 Carl Sagan Summer School Workshop](#)
- April 2010: [Public Tours, Armagh Observatory, Armagh Heritage Day](#)

2009

- Sep. 2009: [Public tour, Armagh Observatory, European Heritage Day](#)
- Aug. 2009: [Staff photo, Armagh Observatory](#)
- June - July 2009: [MiNDSTEp Observations at DK/1.54m ESO/La Silla Observatory, Chile](#)
- May 2009: [Public tours, Armagh Observatory, Armagh Heritage Day](#)
- April 2009: [Public tours Cross-border Science School Conference, Armagh Observatory, UK](#)
- Feb. 2009: [Workshop on High-Performance Computing at ICHEC](#)

2008

- Sep. 2008: [Poster presentation at DPS annual meeting, Cornell University, USA](#)
- June - July 2008: [MiNDSTEp Observations at DK/1.54m ESO/La Silla Observatory, Chile](#)
- March/April 2008: [Poster presentation at the RAS/National Astronomy Meeting, Queens University Belfast, UK](#)
- Jan. 2008: [Workshop at Manchester Microlensing Conference, UK](#)

2007

- Oct. 2007: [Microlensing Workshop, Toulouse, France](#)
- Sep. 2007: [Public tour, Armagh Observatory, European Heritage Day](#)
- July 2007: [Staff photo, Armagh Observatory](#)
- June - July 2007: [MiNDSTEp Observations at DK/1.54m ESO/La Silla Observatory, Chile](#)
- May 2007: [Public tours, Armagh Observatory, Armagh Heritage Day](#)
- April 2007: [Talk at the ASGI meeting at Queens University Belfast, UK](#)
- March 2007: [Public tours Cross-border Science School Conference, Armagh Observatory, UK](#)
- Jan. 2007: [Poster presentation at the Lindsay Centennial Symposium, Armagh Observatory, UK](#)

2006

- Oct. 2006: [Start of PhD studies at Armagh Observatory, UK](#)
- Aug. 2006: [Offer on PhD Scholarship from International Max-Planck Research School \(IMPRS\), Katlenburg-Lindau, Germany](#)
- Aug. 2006: [Offer on PhD Scholarship from Armagh Observatory, UK](#)
- June 2006: [Poster presentation, Danish Physical Society](#)
- June - Sep. 2006: [IDA Research Assistant, Niels Bohr Institute, University of Copenhagen, Denmark](#)
- April 2006: [MSc thesis defence, Institute colloquium](#)
- March 2006: [Talk at 1st SONG workshop on early detection of microlensing events](#)
- Jan. 2006: [2006 NORDITA Astrobiology Winter School, Finland](#)

2005

- Sep. 2005: [Poster presentation at DPS, Cambridge, UK \(Particle dynamics within the habitable zone of extrasolar planetary systems\)](#)

2002

- Feb. 2002: [Poster presentation at Exoplanet workshop held in DLR/Berlin/Germany](#)